

Research Article

Analysis of Student Discipline Character Implementation in Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School

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Abstract

This research aims to: 1) analyze the cultivation of students' disciplinary character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School, 2) identify supporting factors and inhibiting factors for the cultivation of students' disciplinary character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School, and 3) analyzing solutions in overcoming obstacles that occur in cultivating students' disciplined character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. This research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. This research is located at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. Determination of research subjects was carried out purposively, consisting of: 1) Principal, 2) Deputy principal for student affairs, 3) Deputy principal for curriculum, 4) Pancasila and citizenship education teacher and Islamic religious education teacher at analyzing solutions in overcoming obstacles that occur in cultivating students' disciplined character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School, and 5) Students in Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. Data collection in this research was carried out using observation, interviews and documentation techniques. The results of this research show that: 1) the cultivation of students' disciplined character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is carried out in a programmed and planned manner in learning and outside of learning; 2) Supporting factors for cultivating disciplinary character, namely that all students are required to live in Islamic boarding schools, the school cares about disciplinary character; 3) Inhibiting factors for cultivating disciplinary character are students' different backgrounds, lack of student awareness regarding disciplinary character; 4) The solution to overcoming obstacles is holding a program to introduce the madrasa environment, providing socialization and motivation to all students.

Keywords: Discipline Character Cultivation, Islamic Based Junior High School, Curriculum.

Introduction

Current developments in science and technology leave various problems that need attention. Modern society has succeeded in developing science and technology to become an alternative solution to the problems of everyday life, but in other conditions increasingly sophisticated science and technology are less able to foster noble morality and religiosity. This is supported by research from (Mayeni *et al.*, 2019, pp. 239-246) which states that the use of technology among teenagers, apart from having a positive impact, also has a negative impact, namely causing character values to decline. Noble morals such as honesty, truth, mutual help, tolerance and justice have begun to be eroded by fraud, hostility, oppression and other disgraceful acts (Daulay, 2012, p. 141). Efforts to instill character values can be obtained by students through education at school. Schools as educational institutions have an important role in shaping the character of students through the education and teaching process. Education is a process of transferring knowledge, transforming values, and forming personality with all the aspects it covers. Education is a process necessary to obtain balance and perfection in individual development in society (Nurkholis, 2013). Students who take education will acquire the knowledge, skills and habits to create knowledgeable, creative and socially ethical humans which are shared by all of humanity.

Education is all learning experiences that take place in all environments and throughout life. Conceptually, education is very important in developing human qualities (Mudyahardjo, 2013, p. 3). This is in accordance with Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system. Education is an effort to lead

students towards a process of maturity in various aspects. Schools have two main functions, namely as a place of education and an institution for socialization. Based on these two functions, the influence of schools on students is not only limited to the transfer of knowledge, but the atmosphere of the school environment and the education system implemented will also influence students' development (Annisa, 2018). Education has two main functions, namely as a transfer of values and a transfer of knowledge. Value transfer, namely the world of education is expected to be able to transfer values, norms and noble character. Knowledge transfer, namely the world of education, is expected to be able to transfer knowledge and technology to students (Iskarim, 2016, p. 3).

Character education is a process of transforming life values to be developed in a person's personality so that they become integrated into a person's life behavior (Saptono, 2011, p. 23). Character education consists of operative values, values that function in practice and experience growth which makes a value into character, a character that can be relied upon and used to respond to various situations in a moral way (Lickona, 2014, p. 22). It is this process that character is then linked to education, both education in the family, school and society. Schools that want to build character education must provide a good moral environment because school is the second home for children after family.

Schools as formal educational institutions need to pay special attention to education, especially related to character education. This is in accordance with (Johansson *et al.*, 2011, p.3) which states that schools are institutions that have long been seen as institutions to prepare students for life, both academically and as moral agents in society. Schools expect children to obey rules in general, but discipline is generally carried out for one incident and reminds students to obey a rule (Goodman, 2007, p.7). School is one of the educational institutions that carries out the task of developing character values. These character values include honesty, openness, tolerance, wisdom, self-discipline, usefulness, mutual help and compassion, courage, and democratic values (Lickona, 2013, pp. 45-46). The number of character values that need to be instilled, self-discipline is one of the character values that is important to develop (Wuryandani *et al.*, 2014, p. 287). Schools are seen as institutions to prepare children academically and as moral agents in society (Johansson *et al.*, 2011, p. 109). This means that to become capable and moral citizens, children need to be educated to learn moral values and discipline.

Schools have the authority to shape and educate students to be much better. This is reinforced by (Lickona *et al.*, 2013, p.72-89) which states that schools that want to build character must provide a moral environment that emphasizes good values and places them at the forefront. Respect and responsibility and the values that come from both are values that can be taught by schools. Character education really needs to be implemented in schools because through character education a society that is religious, strong, has noble character and is strong will be created. Implementing character education in schools can be done in various ways, namely through integration into learning, integration into self-development programs, and integration into school culture. Tambanun *et al.*, (2022) states that the integration of character education through learning includes the introduction of values, awareness of the importance of values, and internalization of values into student behavior through learning.

Character education can be integrated into the implementation of learning. Pancasila and citizenship education is one of the subjects that has an important role in implementing and strengthening the character of students. The presence of the Pancasila and citizenship education curriculum seeks to instill the attitudes of Indonesian citizens, especially the younger generation, to have insight and awareness of nationality and love for the homeland as the embodiment of responsible citizens, who have insight and appreciation for the diversity of Indonesian society so that they are able to communicate well to strengthen the integration of the nation. Have insight, awareness, obligations, skills in carrying out rights, responsibilities and participation as citizens who are intelligent, skilled and also have character.

Pancasila and citizenship education is an inherent part of the instrumentation and praxis of national education to educate the life of the Indonesian nation through the corridor of value base education (Juliardi, 2015, p. 124). Moreover, in Islamic Junior High School, Pancasila and citizenship education subjects aim to shape students into complete individuals who have the norms of life as individual and social creatures. This is supported by Lestari *et al.*, (2019) which states that Islamic boarding school-based character education through learning Pancasila and citizenship education is implemented through the planning stage, namely by including character values in the RPP, the implementation stage by instilling religious character values, discipline, honesty and curiosity, the evaluation stage by using classroom observations and conducting follow-up outside the classroom. Pancasila and citizenship education is formulated broadly to include the

process of preparing the younger generation to take on their roles and responsibilities as citizens, and specifically the role of education in schooling, teaching and learning in the process of preparing good and moral citizens (Mashau *et al.*, 2017, p. 2). Pancasila and citizenship education cannot be separated from the framework of national identity and develops an attitude of respect for diversity, collaborative learning and creativity.

Integrating character into students can be carried out by subject teachers by providing various motivations, structured guidance and example. This means that teachers have a very important role in shaping students' disciplined character. Helmawati (2016: 98) states that the presence of teachers is absolutely necessary, if there are only students, but there are no teachers, then there will be no teaching and learning activities at school. The task of educators in Islam is considered something very noble. Moreover, disciplined character is very important to form in students because it will produce graduates who have achievements and character.

The character of discipline among teenagers, especially students, experiences serious problems that can damage the character of the Indonesian nation, including cheating on exams, insulting friends (bullying), lying to teachers, violating school rules, truancy, not doing school work, brawls, and free association among students. These cases still often occur in schools in both urban and rural environments. Berliani and Sudrajat (2018) explains that juvenile delinquency in this modern era has exceeded reasonable limits. Many students, especially in junior high school, are familiar with smoking, drugs, free sex, and are involved in many criminal acts. Apart from that, a lot of bullying behavior in schools can trigger divisions and result in moral and psychological pressure on students who end up leaving school.

The morality crisis experienced by students is closely related to other multidimensional crises faced by this nation in general and national education in particular. If examined and assessed more objectively, the student morality crisis is a reflection of a wider crisis that is deeply rooted in society in general. The crisis experienced by students at the school level, both primary, secondary and higher education, is a reflection of the broader crisis in societal morality. It can be assumed that efforts to overcome this problem will not be adequate if only carried out in the school environment. There must be synergy to overcome these problems in the wider community, in the household and in the environment (Mayeni *et al.*, 2019). This problem needs to be overcome through instilling and strengthening students' disciplined character so that good character will be formed. It is through good disciplined character that the development of civilization can run well.

The disciplined character of students in schools needs to be implemented and developed to create a conducive atmosphere, especially in learning. Purboretno (2022, p. 98) says discipline is a condition that is created and formed through the process of a series of behaviors that demonstrate the values of obedience, compliance, loyalty, regularity and order. Discipline can create order, guarantee discipline in justice, and follow spiritual development (Mashau *et al.*, 2017, p. 2). Discipline is a condition that is created and formed through several behaviors, where with discipline students will better understand how important it is to use their time well. Adeyemi *et al.*, (2009) interprets that disciplined character is an attitude and behavior that arises as a result of training or the habit of obeying rules, laws or orders. Disciplined character can be defined as a good character and brings a person to good things. Students who instill the character of discipline within themselves, then activities in school, society and family will be more focused and orderly.

Discipline character education is an important thing to pay attention to in order to develop a person's character. Armed with disciplined character values will encourage the growth of other good character values, such as responsibility, honesty, cooperation, and so on. Elvianti *et al.*, (2023) suggests that there are three dimensions of discipline, namely (1) discipline to prevent problems; (2) discipline to solve problems so they don't get worse; and (3) discipline to deal with students who behave out of control. Building a disciplined character in the school environment is very important from the first time a child enters school. According to Lestari *et al.*, (2019) that children have been trained to discipline themselves. Children are taught the natural consequences and logical consequences of their actions. Various types of feedback should be given to children, verbally and in action. It's just that punishment should not be given to children. Not only is it detrimental to a child's development, but also effective feedback is not physical punishment.

Currently there are still disciplinary problems in schools, including the problem of many students skipping classes during class hours, not submitting assignments, wearing uniforms that do not comply with school rules and being late for lessons, requiring schools to pay more attention to school discipline values so that discipline is better enforced. The occurrence of undisciplined behavior at school shows that there has been a serious problem in terms of disciplinary character education. The emergence of undisciplined behavior

shows that the knowledge related to character that students gain at school does not have a positive impact on changes in student behavior in everyday life (Wuryandani *et al.*, 2014, pp. 286–287).

Character values refer to the fundamental beliefs and perspectives that guide persons in their behavior and interactions with others. The psychological and socio-cultural configuration of an individual may be influenced by these character values (Kusnadi, 2023, p. 227). Character education must be implemented in synergy and continuously. In school, character education must be designed holistically, so that when students enter a new region and climate as new students, they can follow a holistic education process that can turn them into students with noble character as designed by the school. This is where the development of a model, method, or strategy for appropriate and accurate character education is important for realizing the planned objectives of character education (Marzuki and Samsuri, 2022, p. 123). Basically, students know that their behavior is not correct but they do not have the ability to get used to avoiding this wrong behavior. This is a process of student character education that occurs. It could be that the character education that has been carried out so far has only reached the knowledge stage, and has not yet reached the feeling and behavior of character.

The author obtained data on student discipline at school to see whether religious character and discipline had been implemented at school. Even though the character of discipline has been implemented in schools, there are still problems with student discipline in schools, such as the large number of students who play truant or do not come to school, are late for school, and are not disciplined in dressing and learning in class. Based on data obtained by the author in the "Daily Report on the Condition of Madrasah An Nur Students for the 2020/2021 Academic Year" shows that the number of students in grades VII-IX who missed school was 65 students and the total number of students during one semester was above 200. This proves that Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is still not optimal in instilling discipline in students. The existence of supporting and inhibiting factors in cultivating students' disciplined character is something that influences the success of character education. Therefore, it is necessary to dig deeper into the problem of cultivating the disciplined character of Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students so that it is in accordance with what is expected. Looking at the problems presented by the author above, the author is interested in conducting research on cultivating students' disciplined character at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School.

Research Method

The type of research used in this research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. The researcher describes the cultivation of the disciplined character of Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students in each work program. In addition, this research identifies supporting and inhibiting factors in cultivating the disciplined character of students at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach. The aim of this research is to provide information in the form of descriptive data regarding the cultivation of students' disciplined character at the Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. The subjects in this research were the principal, teachers and students of Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School.

Research Results and Discussion

Instilling character values in schools is a school effort to build student character. This is in line with Rachman and Lestari (2017: 20) which states that character education is a conscious and planned effort to create an atmosphere, a process of empowering potential and acculturating students to build personal character as citizens. One of the character values developed in schools is the character value of discipline. Disciplined character is responsible social behavior and optimal independent function in a social relationship that develops on the basis of the ability to manage, motivate and self-independence (Darmuin, 2012, p. 49). Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School instills the character of discipline in a planned and programmed manner through learning in the classroom and outside the classroom. Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School gives responsibility to all school members to care about instilling the value of disciplined character in all students.

Schools are educational institutions that instill character values through school culture in students to achieve common goals. The Ministry of National Education issued 18 character values that must be developed in cultural and character education, one of which is the value of discipline. Implementation of character education values in schools is carried out through planning, implementation and evaluation stages (Wibowo, 2012). The instilling of disciplinary character values in students at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is carried out through planning, implementation and evaluation stages which are

carried out thoroughly both in and outside of learning. This is in accordance with Rachman and Lestari (2015: 21) which states that at a macro level character development can be divided into three stages, namely planning, implementation and evaluation of results.

a) Planning

The planning for instilling disciplined character values at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is adjusted to the school's goals or vision. The school's stated goal is to put more emphasis on producing students who are outstanding, knowledgeable, have a Koranic personality, are superior, are disciplined and are independent. This is in accordance with Juliardi's (2015) which states that the achievement of character formation of students is expected to be complete, balanced and integrated in accordance with graduate competency standards. The aim of instilling disciplined character values in Islamic boarding school-based schools is that apart from being experts in the field of knowledge, they must also be experts in morals. This is confirmed by Sholihah (2021) which states that the aim of character education is to improve the quality of educational processes and outcomes which lead to the formation of students' complete character and noble morals.

The planning process for instilling student discipline character values at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School has been well programmed. The initial planning is carried out by the school by making a work program plan for one year as well as a detailed budget of funds to be implemented. The planning process is carried out in all areas involving the entire school community. This is confirmed by Rachman and Lestari (2017: 21) which states that the planning stage carried out was developed through character tools that were explored, crystallized and formulated through various sources. Planning for instilling students' disciplinary character values includes planning inside and outside of learning.

1) In Learning

The planning process for instilling disciplinary character values in learning is carried out by the deputy principal for curriculum and subject teachers. Planning for instilling disciplined character values in learning is in accordance with Daulay's (2012) which explains that the steps for implementing school culture-based character education can, among other things, be implemented by determining the main values of character education, preparing daily and weekly schedules, designing a curriculum adapted to the school (K13), evaluating school regulations, developing school traditions or habits, as well as the development of co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. Wibowo (2012, p.71) says that the curriculum is the core or spirit of education itself. Improvements in the curriculum need to be made to complement deficiencies in the curriculum implemented in schools. Curriculum improvement in question is the development of the existing school curriculum and then adapting it to character education, especially disciplined character.

Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School curriculum deputy made a plan for the religious character values and disciplinary character that he wanted to develop in the school by analyzing, considering and adapting input from the world of education and Islamic boarding schools. If this has been agreed upon, the next step is to socialize the program that wants to be implemented to all teachers as implementers of instilling disciplinary character values in the classroom or through classroom learning. This is in accordance with Listyarti (2012: 10) who explained that one of the steps to instilling character education so that it becomes a school culture is to prepare a comprehensive plan to intensify development and learning through character that the school will achieve or target. The socialization organized by the school was agreed upon by all school members.

A teacher has the responsibility to instill disciplined character values in learning by integrating character values into the material presented in the classroom. This is supported by Darmuin (2012: 20) who explains that one approach to character education is through integrating character education into every learning material presented in the classroom. Each learning material has an instructional impact and an accompanying impact on character education. The teacher makes a plan to instill disciplinary character values through learning tools consisting of lesson plans, syllabus, learning media, and strategies/methods used to attract students' attention in class. This is supported by Listyarti (2012: 10-11) which states that one of the steps in instilling character education into school culture is through a workshop, all teachers must determine a clear approach or method in subjects that can be used to instill character education that has been agreed upon by the school.

Pancasila and citizenship education are subjects as character education, of course the teacher's role is very important to guide and educate so that all students have good character. Susiatic (2013: 20) explained that

one of the missions of Pancasila and citizenship education is character education, in addition to political education, moral education and legal education at every level of education. This is confirmed by Juliardi (2015: 120) who said that Pancasila and citizenship education has a position as the spearhead in character education, where character education must be the goal of learning. The Pancasila and citizenship education teacher Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School plans learning that integrates disciplinary character values by preparing learning tools.

Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School teachers prepare plans according to those directed by the head of the curriculum so that the program they want to run during classroom learning can be planned and structured. This is confirmed by Adeyemi *et al.*, (2009) explains that character education must be part of the curriculum and always be embedded in all subject matter divisions or across the curriculum. This means that the character values that will be instilled in all students must be explicitly stated in the curriculum developed by the school and by teachers which includes annual, semester, weekly and daily programs.

Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School uses a national curriculum that has been synchronized with Islamic boarding school culture so that the discipline character values developed at the school have been planned from the start to shape the religious and disciplined character of all students. The instillation of disciplinary character values at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School has been programmed and focused at each level so that the instillation of disciplinary character values in students is differentiated at each level, such as the extracurricular activity program organized by the school.

The results of the research show that the planning for instilling religious values and students' disciplined character in learning has been carried out well by the head of curriculum and teachers at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. The teacher includes and instills religious character and discipline in the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP). The learning implementation plan has been planned carefully and optimally by the civics teacher, but when in the classroom or in practice there are several obstacles because success in carrying out disciplined character values is of course supported by students as a determinant of the success of character cultivation. PPKn teachers have also included the value of students' disciplined character in the RPP which is linked to the learning material taught using methods or strategies that attract students. Through this, it can be concluded that the planning for instilling disciplined character values in learning has been well planned by Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School.

2) Outside Learning

The planning process for instilling students' disciplined character values outside of learning is carried out by the head of student affairs, guidance and counseling teachers and also assisted by all school members. The deputy principal for student affairs made a plan to instill students' disciplined character values by compiling a number of work programs through internal meetings taking into account the vision and mission at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. After holding an internal meeting attended by the school principal, head of student affairs, head of curriculum, teacher representatives and the Islamic boarding school foundation to get an agreement on the activity program, the next step is to make a school work plan for one learning year. This is in Wahono and Priyanto (2017) which states that school culture is an important element in a school and is influenced by the values and beliefs that become the principles and vision of the school. The structure and systems in schools provide the school with the opportunity to determine how to carry out its existing vision.

The deputy principal for student affairs at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is also focused on instilling the value of disciplinary character in students by formulating school rules, applying credit for violation points, and implementing a remission program which is planned to instill the value of disciplinary character in students. All programs planned by the deputy principal for student affairs require careful processes and planning so that they can be implemented into a good school culture. This is as said by Komariah (2011: 93) which explains that planning is making targets that will be achieved or achieved in the future.

Planning activities for the program to instill students' disciplinary character values outside of learning refers to the types of activities that include elements such as goals, targets, substance of activities, implementation of activities, related parties, mechanisms for implementation, time and place, and supporting facilities. Planning for instilling disciplinary character values at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is carried out as closely as possible, namely by making the entire academic community in the school more effective to support the achievement of the process of instilling disciplinary character values in students. As

said by Wiyani (2012) which states that effective planning in program preparation is carried out through a series of questions that need to be answered such as what activities must be carried out, where the activities will be carried out, when the activities will be carried out, who will do them, why they will be carried out, and how they will be carried out.

Budimansyah (2010: 62) explains that the character education process which is carried out formally, is packaged in learning and learning interactions (outside of learning) which are deliberately designed to achieve the goals of character education by implementing various structured activities. To achieve the goals of character education, namely by preparing the management of character education, especially religious and discipline, namely through preparing the management of disciplinary character education. This is done through curriculum planning, designing program activities to instill students' disciplinary character values outside of learning in a programmed and structured manner. Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School has implemented this planning carefully and programmatically in every activity of instilling religious values and discipline, including by formulating school rules, creating credit points for violations and remission programs, and preparing planned extracurricular activities to instill values of student discipline character.

Looking at the plans that have been prepared by Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School, it can be said that the planning stage of instilling students' disciplinary character values outside of learning has been running effectively and has been well planned. The school has tried to prepare a good and directed plan, namely by planning a program for cultivating disciplinary character values that is in accordance with character education management standards.

b) Implementation

Character education can be applied in schools through learning in the classroom and outside the classroom. The character education process is based on psychological totality which includes all human individual potential (cognitive, affective, psychomotor) and socio-cultural totality in the context of interactions within educational units, families and society (Lickona, 2013, p. 25). One of the character education implemented in schools is religious character and discipline (Azzet, 2011, p. 17).

The implementation of instilling students' disciplinary values was carried out as a follow-up to the plans that had previously been prepared. Good planning will not work well without good implementation too. The process of instilling disciplinary character values in Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students is carried out through coaching, habituation (self-development), example, integrating disciplinary character values into subjects, initiation, through giving structured assignments in class, through extracurricular activities, and other activity programs. The implementation of instilling students' disciplinary character values is coordinated by the deputy principal for curriculum and carried out by all subject teachers during learning. The implementation of instilling students' disciplinary character values outside of learning is coordinated by the deputy principal for student affairs as the person responsible for each program for instilling students' disciplinary character values outside of learning.

In the implementation of instilling disciplined character values, there are supporting factors. Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School has supporting factors to instill discipline character values in students so that there are 6 supporting factors, including that all Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students are required to live in Islamic boarding schools, the school's concern for instilling character values student discipline, the majority of educators are alumni of the An Nur Bantul Islamic boarding school, there is support from parents and guardians of students, there is support from the community around the school, and adequate school facilities.

The school's concern for instilling disciplinary character values in students. Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School seriously prepares various activity programs that become school habits or culture by implementing them every day. All students and school residents instill the character values at school. The activity program that is used as a habit every day has the aim of making students have good disciplinary character so that the school has good quality. This is in line with the statement from Elvianti *et al.*, (2023) which shares elements of school culture, one of which is through positive school culture in the form of activities that support improving the quality of education. There is support from parents and guardians of students. Parents and guardians have a very important role in supporting their children to obey the rules or regulations at school in the hope that their children will have good religious character and discipline. There are factors inhibiting the implementation of the disciplinary character values of Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul

Islamic Junior High School students. These inhibiting factors are due to internal and external factors that exist in the school. One of the goals of an Islamic boarding school is to create and develop a Muslim personality who has faith and devotion to God, has noble character, and is beneficial to society. However, in reality there are still differences in the conditions of students at school Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students have different backgrounds consisting of various regions, not only from the island of Java. Students have different characters who come from various regions so it is quite difficult to guide them.

Darmuin (2012) explained that one of the cultures that must be developed in schools is academic culture, which means school principals, teachers and students always adhere to theoretical policies in thinking, behaving and acting in everyday life with a mutual agreement. This is in contrast to the reality at school. The lack of student awareness regarding the importance of disciplinary character values is the main weakness at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. There are still many rules that are violated by students at school, proving that there is still a lack of awareness among students. Apart from the rules that are violated, there are still many students who do not take part in the habituation programs at school, one of which is reading the Dzikir in the school yard and there are still many students who play truant while learning is still in progress.

Helmawati (2016) said that parental support is really needed for children to be able to achieve good learning achievements as expected. Parental support has a psychological influence on children in their learning activities. Through parental support, children will be more active and enthusiastic in learning and achieving their dreams. This support takes the form of moral support including attention, affection, example, direction and guidance, enthusiasm and self-confidence. This is in contrast to the reality at school. Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School still has students whose parents force them to go to school and live in Islamic boarding schools. This problem results in students deliberately breaking school rules with the aim of being expelled from school. The child actually didn't like reciting the Koran and was naughty, so he was sent to an Islamic boarding school so that it was as if the school and the boarding school had become a workshop.

Based on the research results, there are several solutions implemented by schools to overcome obstacles in implementing the values of disciplinary character instilling students, including the school holding a student orientation period (MOS), introducing the madrasa environment where there is a fortasi (santri ta'aruf forum) and there is an MPLM (mass introduction to the madrasa environment). Imron (2023) stated that orientation is an introduction that includes the physical environment of the school and the social environment of the school. The aim of holding a student orientation period is regulated in Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 55 of 2014 where the student orientation period aims to introduce school programs, ways of learning, instilling the concept of self-knowledge in accordance with national education goals. Through the program held by the school, the hope is that when you enter the madrasa you will know what values the school applies, the school's rules and regulations, all students will know each other so that the activity program at the school can run well.

Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School continues to provide outreach and motivation to all students. This is done because if something is carried out or done not in the student's heart, the student will feel forced to instill the values instilled at school. This is as said by Johansson *et al.*, (2011) motivation really determines the level of success or failure of student learning outcomes. A student who does not have motivation to learn will not be able to carry out learning activities. Motivation can be provided by schools or socialization teachers, namely through interactive lecture methods, question and answer methods, and video display methods (Azra and Jamil, 2015).

The acquisition of values or character by students can occur if there is verbal or non-verbal communication between educators and students. Instilling disciplinary character values can be carried out by teachers through strategies, methods and approaches that can be used to transfer values to students (Berliani and Sudrajat, 2018). The method of approaching students is carried out by Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School teachers directly in collaboration with the class teacher, student affairs teacher and guidance and counseling (BK) teacher.

The school provides guidance by bringing in parents of students who are forced to live at the An Nur Islamic boarding school and at the same time as attending Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School. Through this, the school hopes that there will be no more cases of students deliberately violating school rules because they are forced to go to school and live in Islamic boarding schools.

Conclusions

Based on the description of the research results and discussion related to the analysis of the instillation of religious values and the disciplined character of students at the Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- 1) The instilling of students' disciplined character values at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School is carried out in learning and outside of learning. Instilling students' disciplinary character values includes three stages, namely planning, implementation and evaluation. The planning stage begins with preparing a work program for one year. In learning, the curriculum is developed and followed up by the teacher by compiling learning tools by integrating disciplinary values into learning. Outside of learning, it is carried out by planning activity programs that serve as a reflection at school every day and drafting school rules and regulations.
- 2) Supporting factors for instilling disciplinary character in at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students include all at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students being required to live in Islamic boarding schools, the school's concern for instilling religious values and disciplinary character students, the majority of educators are alumni of the An Nur Bantul Islamic boarding school, there is support from parents and guardians of students, there is support from the community around the school, and adequate school facilities.
- 3) Factors inhibiting the instillation of religious values and disciplined character in students at Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School due to internal and external factors in the school including the different backgrounds of students, lack of student awareness regarding the importance of the value of disciplined character, the existence of coercion from parents to go to school and live in Islamic boarding schools, many students who sleep or fall asleep in class while learning is taking place due to the need to carry out various boarding school curriculum development programs, lack of coordination between schools and Islamic boarding schools, the existence of vacancies in teaching staff (guidance and counseling teachers), and the school does not yet have mobile CCTV so supervision is still limited.
- 4) The right solution so that the implementation of instilling religious values and the disciplined character of Al Ma'had An Nur Bantul Islamic Junior High School students can run smoothly includes holding a madrasa environment introduction program where there is a fortasi (santri ta'aruf forum) and there is an MPLM (mass introduction to the madrasa environment), continuing to provide socialization and motivation to all students, providing guidance by bringing in parents of students who are forced to live at the An Nur Islamic boarding school, teachers use interesting methods, media and strategies in learning, there are sanctions in the form of a point system according to the mutual agreement that was conveyed during the initial learning contract, increasing coordination between schools and Islamic boarding schools.

Declarations

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